

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF NATIONAL AND UNIVERSAL VALUES IN THE SPIRITUAL DEVELOPMENT OF YOUNG PEOPLE

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Abstract: Differentiation in teaching is a proactive and purposeful strategy where educators tailor instruction to meet the diverse learning needs of students by adjusting the content, process, product, and/or learning environment. It acknowledges that students vary in readiness, interest, and learning profile and aims to provide a range of appropriate challenges and supports so that all students, regardless of their background or ability, can access the curriculum, learn effectively, and grow.

Keywords: Differentiation, education system, generic strategies, **Bloom's Taxonomy**, intellectual behavior, **learning environment**

Introduction: Currently, more and more attention is paid to the introduction of new, non-traditional teaching methods in the education system, as well as modern pedagogical technologies that teach students how to find, learn and draw conclusions. These non-traditional methods should be aimed at the acquisition of active and independent knowledge, the development of thinking and the development of scientific views. It is also necessary to pay more attention to scientific and methodological activities to increase the effectiveness of the educational process. Currently, the education system is one of the main and priority tasks of educational institutions for the development of students' abilities in each subject in each subject. It is not enough to equip students only with knowledge and skills. In the context of modern globalization, the training of highly qualified personnel and the training of modern competitive specialists meeting the requirements of SES, the education system poses a number of tasks. Research and studies have shown that traditional education, based on the active work of the teacher in the classroom and focusing only on the idea of unification, aimed at obtaining ready-made knowledge, is not justified in practice.

Materials and methods: Assessment and instruction are inseparable: the teacher views everything that a student says or does as useful information to understand the learner and craft their effective instruction for that learner (differentiation of instruction stems from effective and ongoing assessment of learner needs).

All students participate in 'respectful' work: each student needs to be involved in challenging tasks that are equally interesting and engaging, to offer equal access to essential understanding and skills.

Students and teachers are collaborators in learning: the teacher studies their students to ascertain what works and what doesn't work for them and continually involves students in decision-making about the classroom (as a result students become more independent learners).

The teacher uses flexible grouping options: they plan student working arrangements that vary widely and purposefully often over relatively short periods of time, for example, whole-class, small group and one-on-one arrangements are used (the flexible grouping of students helps ensure access to a wide variety of learning opportunities and working arrangements).

The teacher focuses on the essentials: they provide clarity about what is essential for students to know, understand and do.

The teacher modifies content, process and products: they find key opportunities to meet learners where they are 'at' in order to propel them forward in knowledge, understanding and skill.

How can we differentiate instruction?

According to **Carol Ann Tomlinson**, there are **four** ways in which teachers may differentiate their instruction.

1. Content: There are six levels of **Bloom's Taxonomy** (a classification of degrees of intellectual [behavior](#) ranging from lower-order thinking skills to higher-order thinking skills of advanced learners) i.e. remembering, conceptual understanding, applying, analyzing, evaluating, and creating. Therefore, according to Carol Ann Tomlinson, the teachers must differentiate the content by creating activities for each group of students covering different levels of **Bloom's Taxonomy**.

2. Process: Every student has a preferred style of learning, and successful **differentiation** allows the delivery of instruction to different mediums of learning (we are not advocating for learning styles!): auditory learners, visual, verbal and kinesthetic learners. This [process-related strategy](#) also considers the fact that each student demands a different amount of [support](#) from the instructor, and they may choose to work individually, in groups or pairs. Carol Ann Tomlinson believes that teachers may improve learning by providing support based on the **individual needs** of each student. The universal thinking framework enables teachers to design different learning journeys that achieve the same goal. Instead of using [generic strategies](#) for everyone, teachers can move pupils from an introductory level to a more advanced understanding of the content using the learning actions. Advanced learners can be stretched and challenged using the red icons that indicate higher-order thinking.

3. Product: After completing a lesson, the students create a **product** to show content mastery. It may be in the form of reports, projects, tests or any other activity. For example, according to Carol Ann Tomlinson, the teachers may ask students to complete [activities](#) to show **mastery** of science lessons as preferred by the students, depending upon their preferred learning style.

4. Learning environment: The optimal learning conditions include both **psychological** and **physical** elements. A **differentiated classroom layout** is crucial, including a wide range of arrangements and classroom furniture to support both personal and group work. Carol Ann Tomlinson states that to support [students' psychological wellbeing](#), teachers must use that classroom management and [teaching strategies](#) that promote a **supportive** and **safe** learning environment.

List of used literature and sources:

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